

OVERCOMING THE DIFFICULTIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE AND THE WAYS OF IMPLEMENTING NEW EXPERIENCES INTO OUR EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article discusses the problems of teaching English in our educational process.

Keywords: teaching English as a second language, challenges in teaching English, TESL, demotivated students, overcoming teaching problems, solutions for key issues.

Introduction. Teaching English as a second language and becoming fluent in English are really different sides of the coin. Because being perfect is not the only way of success in terms of teaching. While teaching English educators need not only enough knowledge but also teaching qualifications. So methodology of TESL is one of the spheres you have to learn.

Every novice teacher faces difficulties during the teaching process like lack of eagerness of students to learn the language or inappropriate atmosphere in the classroom. All these reasons might discourage them to work as a teacher. Different behaviour of students and their attitudes to the lessons, work atmosphere at school, all are the reasons which can affect the teaching process of English language teachers. And how to tackle these problems and how to organise effective lessons?

Methods of analysis. From my own experience I can surely say that in order to have effective English class teachers must have powerful methodology and experience.

But both of them can be gained after working in the sphere. And how the future teachers can be ready beforehand not to have problematic situations in the long term. From my point of view conducting researches is the perfect way of this. If you follow the experienced ESOL teachers and learn their methods, ways of teaching you will be aware about the events which might happen during the lesson and prepare yourself psychologically to them.

Keeping diaries, making notes about teaching process, thinking about dilemmas, exchanging ideas with other experienced teachers can be helpful. But they are not all instead of following others way of teaching you should create your private one.

English is a lively language and teaching it also should be lively and funny process. But after even hard work or sacrificing you might not have the expected results. The truth about teaching is that teacher can see the fruitful result after some amount of time. This may be painful, stressful and energy-consuming process but the final result can make you rewarded.³³

The next rule you have to follow is that to accept the situation physically and psychologically after starting as a teacher. In most cases the atmosphere in the classroom or the relationship among colleagues may not be same as you expected. But you have to overcome all these difficulties with your patience and qualifications. For example disobedient students can make you angry or even nervous and the lesson may be different than you planned.

Students must communicate their needs to teachers on a yearly basis, which is a difficult undertaking. Some children are naturally good at it; they are able to communicate their needs and wants in an interesting way and receive them. Many people, however, find it difficult to interact with their teachers in an efficient manner. Teachers need to establish trust with their pupils and constantly work on their communication skills because they are the more experienced members of the group. Not just between yourself and your kids, but also between themselves and their parents, you are creating a productive communication channel. The school year is filled with fun learning opportunities and trips for the students. And you'll spend the most of the year building relationships with your kids.

However, there will be times when you have to inspire your kids to get through the challenging periods of the year. High school kids, for instance, are overloaded with exams and tasks that will determine their careers. Preschoolers, however, must overcome difficulties including pen grips and ball skills. Both age groups require a trusted teacher's reassuring shoulder.

³³ .Burkhanova M.G. (2022). AXIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDENT MORALITY. European journal of research development and sustainability. Vol 3 N 2. <https://www.scholarzest.com/>

It can be difficult and time-consuming to discipline children in the classroom. Even while you can be sure that your class will be filled with adorable kids, it's also typical to run into students who are rude and lack respect.³⁴

However, you must also be cautious in how you handle disruptions and discipline students. Disrespectful students can destroy your passion for teaching. Implementing justifiable penalties, identifying the source of the issue, involving parents, and developing intervention plans are all effective ways to deal with lack of manners in your classroom.

If you recall anything about your school days, it was probably the fact that teachers were constantly swamped with marking and grading papers. Sick days also aren't always an option. Unfortunately, marking papers isn't something that teachers do during class, so they frequently have to finish marking after class is over.

Documentation entails recording your pupils' development over the course of the year in order to account for their growth. Individual evaluations must also be documented in addition to the teaching notes, and this duty frequently necessitates late nights and weekends.

Being on your feet all day is a requirement for the work of teaching, and there is frequently little opportunity for respite. You must therefore keep busy bees' thoughts engaged in addition to being on your feet.

Results and analysis. Making your work as a teacher easier requires coming up with inventive strategies to keep kids amused. Planning and time management are important in this situation. The same as with high school students, time management entails creating an engaging timetable that covers the year's work without skipping over subject.

Teachers must continuously think outside the box since teaching has become a very competitive industry.³⁵ Everyone at the school is in a competitive environment, and many teachers believe they must accomplish more each year.

In addition to the competition, teachers are completely in charge of a student's development, growth indicators, and disciplinary issues; this puts a lot of strain on a teacher's shoulders.

It's no secret that teaching can be a hard career. Teachers frequently face burnout due to the constant pressure to deliver excellent results. But how can you tell whether you have the condition? Here are a few indicators of burnout among educators: dreaded going into work every day, feeling exhausted after working on lesson planning or

³⁴ Aitchison, J. (1972) *General Linguistics*, English Universities Press.

³⁵ Aitchison, J. (1978) *Linguistics*, Hodder & Stoughton, 2nd edn.

grading papers, and wishing you could quit your job and find something else to do with your life.³⁶

Literature analysis. In spite of this, the reality remains that at 21st century. "Revolution" took place in Russia. Pertaining to how English is taught. Previously, A complete list of all the priorities was given to Grammar, nearly mechanical vocabulary knowledge, reading, and literary translation are all required.

These are the "old school" values, which—to be fair—still produced results, but at what price? Long hours of repetitive labor were required to learn a language.

The exercises, which involved reading the material, translating, memorization of new terms, retelling, and translating exercises, were rather repetitive. On occasion, an essay or dictation is combined with phonetic drills as a break for the sake of the required activity shift. Only one function of the language—the informational one—was accomplished when reading and working on "themes" were prioritized. It is not unexpected that just a small number of people became fluent in the language because only those who were extremely focused and diligent could do so. They could, however, readily compete with Cambridge graduates in grammar! True, they were paid well for their labor; in fact, teaching foreign languages or working as a translator was a particularly esteemed career in our nation.

It now also takes a lot of diligence, patience, and everyday work to acquire this still high social rank. The fact that the majority now has access to language in some way, however, is what is genuinely "revolutionary." The offer is also becoming more and more customer-focused. Why, for instance, would the secretary willfully learn unneeded information about English sentence structure or the palatalization of consonants? A secretary-assistant or manager who works 8 hours a day, or as it is now referred to, "monopoly," in the office, is focused on the acquisition of very specific knowledge and skills, or, more specifically, on the consumption of a certain subset of the market for educational offers for learning English.

Unexpectedly, the public's attention was focused on foreign language teachers as hordes of anxious professionals in many sectors of science, culture, industry, technology, and all other facets of human activity demanded that foreign language instruction begin immediately as a means of production. They are not interested in either the theory or the history of the language; rather, they just need foreign languages, particularly English, for utilitarian purposes in order to interact with individuals from other nations in various aspects of society. The way that education is delivered has also

³⁶ .Burkhanova M.G. (2021). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.02.94.6> Doi:

made things notably easier: going to work, one-on-one lessons with a teacher, visiting a student at home, "weekend" groups, for the busy and not so busy, for "pioneers" and retirees.³⁷ Language universities firmly rely on the core methodology. The translator is never certain of his command of a foreign tongue, but he is completely aware of the unpredictable nature of developing speaking circumstances. When studying using the classical method, students learn to not only work with a wide range of lexical layers but also to view the world as a "native speaker"—a person who is a native speaker.

Conclusion: The conventional strategy for learning a foreign language. In this regard, the traditional technique of learning a foreign language has also undergone certain changes, but the unchanging fundamentals of the "classics" of Russian language approaches have been kept. In schools following other methodological trajectories, they are occasionally actively used. The traditional course, which caters to pupils of various ages, frequently involves learning the language "from scratch." The traditional but crucial duties of a teacher include the development of pronunciation, the establishment of a grammatical foundation, and the removal of communication-impairing psychological and linguistic barriers. "Classics" did not alter the objectives, but the new strategy has already changed the techniques.

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